

Spectrophotometric method for the determination of ziram and zineb with 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN) using Triton X-100 as the solubilizing agent

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A new, rapid, sensitive and selective method has been developed for the determination of ziram and zineb using 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN) as the complexing reagent in the pH range of 8.0–8.5 in the presence of octylphenolpoly(ethylene glycol) ether i.e. Triton X-100. The violet complex shows λ_{\max} at 580 nm. The molar absorptivity is $7.52 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ziram and zineb and Sandell's sensitivity 0.0040 and 0.0036 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for ziram and zineb, respectively. The method has been used for direct determination of ziram and zineb in synthetic mixtures, commercial formulations and crops residue.

We reported earlier spectrophotometric methods which involve the reaction of metal part of pesticide molecule with organic reagents¹. The present method is based on the formation of zinc-thiazolylazo-2-naphthol (Zn-TAN) complex which is insoluble in water but is solubilized by adding Triton X-100 which acts as solubilizing and sensitizing agent. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of ziram and zineb in commercial formulations, crops and synthetic mixtures.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of Zn-TAN complex in Triton X-100 were recorded against the reagent blank. The λ_{\max} was observed at 580 nm in the pH range 8.0–8.5, using 2 ml of 0.001 M TAN. The smaller amounts of TAN gave incomplete complex formation but larger amounts did not increase the absorbance. An insoluble violet Zn-TAN complex was formed which was solubilized in 3.0 ml of 5% Triton X-100. The calibration curve was found to be linear over the concentration range 3.04–42.56 μg for ziram and 2.29–36.64 μg for zineb in 25 ml of final solution.

Five replicate determination on these sample solutions containing 24.32 μg of ziram and 22.90 μg of zineb gave a mean absorbance of 0.24 and 0.25 with S.D. 0.0089, 0.0035 and C.O.V. 3.70%, 1.40%, respectively. The molar absorptivity was found to be $7.52 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ziram and zineb. Sandell's sensitivity for ziram and zineb was found to be 0.0040 and 0.0036 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Interference studies : Various foreign ions were examined for the interference studies of the determination of ziram and zineb. The tolerance limit (μg in parentheses) for alkali metal salts and metal ions were as follows : Ba^{II}, Mo^{VI} (7000); Zr^{II}, Fe^{III} (4500); Mn^{II} (4000); Mg^{II} (580);

V^{IV}(250); U^{VI} (150); Ag^I (90); thiosulphate, citrate (60); tartrate (55); fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, nitrite, oxalate (50); Pb^{II} (30); In^{III} (25); Ni^{II} (20); Co^{II}, Cu^{II} (5). EDTA and pyrophosphate interfered; Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} interfere but masked with 2 ml of sodium thiosulphate; Fe^{II} interfered but masked with 3 ml of 5% NaF solution. Dithiocarbamates such as nabam, dibam, vapam, ferbam and maneb did not interfere in the determination of ziram and zineb.

Applications : The present method has been applied for direct determination of ziram and zineb in the commercial samples and crops residue. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of ziram/zineb

(A) In commercial samples :			
Commercial samples		Amount taken	Amount found ^a
		μg	μg
Ziram (Dhanuka) Z-27		20.0	19.50
		25.0	24.65
		30.0	29.85
Zineb (Indofil) Z-78		12.0	11.85
		14.0	13.75
		18.0	17.50
(B) In crops :			
Sample	Crop ^b	Amount added	Amount found
		μg	μg
Ziram	Cabbage	20.0	19.45
		25.0	24.65
		30.0	29.90
Zineb	Rice	20.0	19.30
		25.0	24.70
		30.0	29.95

^aEach result is a mean of five replicate determinations, ^bamount of crop 10 g.

Conclusion : The present method is quite simple, selective and better than the other known methods². This method can be used for the determination of ziram and zineb at low levels in various commercial formulations, crops and synthetic mixtures. The wide applicability, selectivity, simplicity and rapidity of this method makes it preferable to most of the other methods.

Experimental

A Systronic UV-VIS 118 spectrophotometer and a ECIL model LI-22 pH meter were used.

Ziram and zineb (Wilson Laboratories, Bombay) solutions (1 g dm^{-3}) were prepared in dimethylsulfoxide (A.R., Ranbaxy) and standardized³. A stock solution of 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN) was made in methanol (AnalaR). pH was adjusted by adding sodium acetate and acetic acid buffer solution. A 5% solution of octylphenol-poly(ethylene glycol)ether, i.e. Triton X-100 (Merck, A.R.) was made in double-distilled water.

Procedure : To a solution containing known amount of either ziram or zineb, the reagent (0.001 M ; 2 ml) and the buffer solution (pH 8.0–8.5; 2 ml) were added. The mixture was shaken and then allowed to stand for 2 min to complete the reaction. Then Triton X-100 (5%; 3 ml) was added to solubilize the violet complex formed and finally the volume was made upto 25 ml with double-distilled water and the

absorbance was measured at 580 nm against the reagent blank.

A series of solution containing 0.12 to 1.70 ppm of ziram and 0.09 to 1.46 ppm of zineb were used to construct calibration curves.

Determination of ziram and zineb in crops (rice, wheat and cabbage) :

A known amount of ziram or zineb in 50 ml of DMSO was crushed with 10 g of the crop and the mixture was shaken mechanically for 1 h, filtered and the residue was washed three times with DMSO. All the washings and filtrate were collected and ziram and zineb content were determined by the general procedure. Untreated samples were taken as the reference. The results indicated good recoveries in all the cases. The results of the determination are given in Table 1.

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